

SIMILARITY SEARCH OF FREESOUND ENVIRONMENTAL SOUND BASED ON THEIR ENHANCED MULTISCALE FRACTAL DIMENSION

Motohiro Sunouchi

Graduate School of Information Science and Technology, Hokkaido University,
North 13, West 8, Kita-ku, Sapporo, Japan
sunouchi@meme.hokudai.ac.jp

Yuzuru Tanaka

Meme Media Laboratory, Hokkaido University,
North 13, West 8, Kita-ku, Sapporo, Japan
tanaka@meme.hokudai.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a new acoustic feature signature based on the multiscale fractal dimension extracted from sound signals for the content-based retrieval of environmental sounds such as field-recording sounds shared through Freesound. The multiscale fractal dimension derived from the fractal theory is known as a descriptor representing several features of the sound waveform. We report the basic characteristics of the enhanced multiscale fractal dimension (EMFD) extracted from each sound signal. Furthermore, we developed a similarity search system for environmental sounds using EMFD and Mel frequency cepstral coefficients 39 (MFCC39). We have compared the descriptiveness of EMFD signature and MFCC39 for the search purpose and found some competitive aspects of EMFD signature against MFCC39. These results show that EMFD signature is useful for describing the features of environmental sound and applicable to the search of large-scale sound databases.

1. INTRODUCTION

These days, handy PCM sound recorders are growing popular. Not only music creators but also many amateurs are enjoying recording environmental sounds, sharing them on the web and creating new music by utilizing them. In general, environmental sounds comprise various types of sound, such as those made by creatures, natural phenomenon and machines, city noise, music, speeches and so on. To analyze environmental sounds, various types of acoustic features have been proposed [1–4]. For promoting communications and music creations utilizing database of field-recording sounds on the web, it is important to find appropriate acoustic features for searching tasks that describe timbre, tone and texture of sounds more effectively.

In this paper, we show the method to compute the fractal dimension and the multiscale fractal dimension (MFD) of a sound signal in chapter 2. In chapter 3, we show the process of the development of EMFD based on MFD. In chapter 4, we demonstrate the basic characteristics of EMFD.

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In chapter 5, we show the method to evaluate the descriptiveness of EMFD signature and report the results of the evaluation.

2. MULTISCALE FRACTAL DIMENSION

2.1 Fractal Dimension of a Curve

Mandelbrot, who advocated a concept of fractal, demonstrated that some structures in nature could be modeled well by the theory of fractals [5]. Fractal dimension is one of the numerical values that can describe characteristics of a fractal. The fractal dimension of a straight line, which is a special case of a curve, is 1. In general, the fractal dimension of a curve is defined as a real number between 1 and 2. The fractal dimension of a curve in a two-dimensional space can be calculated as follows.

As an example of a curve, let's take the sound waveform. A covering area can be drawn by a moving disk, whose radius is r , along the curve of waveform. The center of the disk should be at any position on the original waveform curve and the width of the covering area like a belt becomes $2r$. Fig. 1 shows the covering area obtained by moving the disk along the waveform. This covering area is called Minkowski Sausage.

Figure 1. Sound waveform and Minkowski sausage

Let $A(r)$ be the area of Minkowski Sausage obtained by a disk of radius r . We plot $\log A(r)$ with respect to $\log r$ to obtain Fig. 2. For curves in nature such as coastlines, the plot of $\log A(r)$ versus $\log r$ is often like a straight line. Equation (1) shows that the fractal dimension D can be defined as the gradient of the plotted line subtracted from 2.

Figure 2. Double logarithmic plot of $A(r)$ vs. r of Minkowski Sausage

$$D = 2 - \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \frac{\log A(r)}{\log r} \quad (1)$$

2.2 Multiscale Fractal Dimension of Sound Waveform

In practice, sound waveform may have different structures depending on its scale, therefore fractal dimension D may vary by the value of r . Let $\text{grad}(r)$ be the gradient of $\log A(r)$ versus $\log r$, then multiscale fractal dimension (MFD) is defined as function of r by the equation (2).

$$D(r) = 2 - \text{grad}(r) \quad (2)$$

MFD at time t denoted by $D(r, t)$ can be defined for a fixed short time scanning window, say 50msec in this paper, of target sound's waveform. The function $D(r, t)$ is called fractogram. P. Maragos utilized MFDs to reduce the error in speech recognition system using HMM and reported the modest improvement in recognition performance [6]. A. Zlatintsi used MFDs to analyze short-time music signal structures at multiple time scales and concluded that there is a strong evidence that MFDs can well describe the structure and properties of instrument sounds [7].

3. ENHANCED MULTISCALE FRACTAL DIMENSION

We developed the method to compute the signature "enhanced multiscale fractal dimension" (EMFD) of sound based on MFD. The following procedures are performed to compute EMFD. EMFD can be computed as follows.

3.1 Preprocessing a Target Sound

A target sound to analyze should be first normalized with its maximum amplitude to be -0.1db, and converted in the standard format based on the following specifications, the sampling rate (frequency) is chosen to be 44,100hz, while the bit depth is 16bits. We use only a single channel.

3.2 Creating MFDs Profile

To compute the area of Minkowski Sausage, we setup a unit disk vector C_r whose radius is r based on the equation

Figure 3. Mesh-Approximation of a unit disk

Figure 4. Steps for computing the area of Minkowski Sausage at n -th sampling position in the current scanning window by sliding the unit disk of $r=2$.

(3). Fig. 3 shows how the model of unit disk is built. The vector C_r , whose radius is r , includes $2r$ elements that denote the vertical distance from the top to the center of unit disk at each horizontal position.

$$C_r = \left\{ \text{floor} \left(\sqrt{2ri - i^2} \right) \mid i = 0 \rightarrow 2r, i \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4 shows how the area of Minkowski Sausage at the n -th sampling position is computed by sliding the unit disk along the sound signal in the current scanning window. The striped block corresponds to the minimum value at the n -th sampling position that is covered by the unit disk at each discrete step, whereas the gray block corresponds to the maximum value. At each discrete step of sliding the unit disk, the maximum and minimum values at each n -th sampling position are independently updated to keep respectively the maximum value and the minimum value. Let n be the sampling position, r be the radius of the unit disk, $area_n$ be the area of Minkowski Sausage at each sampling position n and $\text{sig}(n)$ be the amplitude value of sound signal at each sampling position n , then $area_n$ is computed by equation (4). MFD is computed using the equation (5) for 132 different discrete values ($r = 1, 2, \dots, 132$). The minimum radius ($r = 1$) corresponds to the sampling period of the sound signal (1/44.1 ms) and the range of different values of r corresponds to the range of the time scales from 1/44.1 to 3 ms.

$$area_n = \max_{step=0 \rightarrow 2r} \{ \text{sig}(n - r + step) + C_r(step) \} - \min_{step=0 \rightarrow 2r} \{ \text{sig}(n - r + step) - C_r(step) \} \quad (4)$$

$$MFD(r) = 2 - \frac{\log \{A(r+1)/A(r)\}}{\log \{(r+1)/r\}} \quad (5)$$

$$swp(sound) = \left\{ 0, 50, \dots, \text{floor} \left(\frac{\text{the length of the sound in milliseconds}}{50} - 1 \right) \times 50 \right\} \quad (6)$$

$$EMFD = \left\{ \frac{\text{card} \{t | 1 + 0.02(dimbin - 1) \leq MFD_t(rbin) < 1 + 0.02dimbin, t \in swp(sound)\}}}{\text{card} \{swp(sound)\}} \right\}_{\substack{dimbin=1 \rightarrow 50 \\ rbin=1 \rightarrow 132}} \quad (7)$$

3.3 Enhanced Multiscale Fractal Dimension

In this paper, we use a fixed width scanning window of length 50ms. The set of fixed scanning windows of the target sound is defined as $swp(sound)$ by equation (6). MFD for each scanning window can be obtained as a vector of length 132, each of which takes a value between 2 and 1. To describe features of various types of environmental sounds using a single type of signature, we define a new signature, namely the enhanced multiscale fractal dimension (EMFD). EMFD is defined as a feature vector computed as the two-dimensional histogram of time-varying MFD values. Each bin contains the percentage of the scanning windows of the target sound. We define 50 bins with a width of 0.02 for the value of the fractal dimension of each scanning window and the 132 bins with a width of 1 for the radius of the unit disk. The value in each bin is computed by equation (7). In the equation (7), the $\text{card}(A)$ returns the cardinality of set A. And $dimbin$ is a counting number that corresponds to the bins for the value of the fractal dimension and $rbin$ is a counting number that corresponds to the bins for the radius of the unit disk. For example, the value of bin whose $dimbin$ is 1 and $rbin$ is 1 is (the number of the scanning windows in which the $MFD(1)$ is between 1 and 1.02) / (the total number of the scanning windows). The equation (8) is always true at each radius of the unit disk. The Fig. 5 is an image which visualizes the EMFD of a cuckoo sound. The higher the value of bin is, the darker the color of the bin is in the figure.

$$\sum_{dimbin=1}^{50} EMFD = 1.0, \text{ at each radius of the unit disk} \quad (8)$$

3.4 Logarithmic EMFD with a Long Time Scale

Furthermore we developed a derived signature to utilize for similarity search task and for the evaluations of the descriptiveness of EMFD in chapter 5. We have analyzed various types of environmental sounds using EMFD and found that EMFD seems to have informative values for larger unit disks than the disk of 3ms radius ($r=132$). We extended the maximum radius of the unit disk to 218 that corresponds to 5 milliseconds ($1/10$ of the period of scanning window) and the discrete values to include $\{r = \text{round}(1.4^x), x = 1, \dots, 16\}$. For the dimensionality reduction of the feature vector, we reduced the number of bins for the $dimbin$ from 50 to 32. We define this 32 ($dimbin$) x 16 ($rbin$) fea-

Figure 5. EMFD histogram of a cuckoo sound

Figure 6. EMFD-LL histogram of a cuckoo sound

ture vector as EMFD-LL. Fig. 6 shows the EMFD-LL histogram of the same cuckoo sound as the one in Fig. 5.

4. BASIC CHARACTERISTICS OF EMFD

To demonstrate the basic characteristics of EMFD and to estimate the robustness of EMFD as a signature, we applied EMFD to test sound signals.

4.1 EMFD of Single Sine Waves

Fig. 7 shows the EMFD histograms of single sine waves of 110hz, 220hz, 440hz, 880hz and 1760hz. The higher the frequency of a signal is, the smaller the value of the radius at the first peak of EMFD histogram becomes. The fractal dimension of a single sine wave converges to 2.0 at the

Figure 7. EMFD histograms of single sine waves of 110hz, 220hz, 440hz, 880hz and 1760hz

Figure 8. Minkowski Sausage by the unit disk with which the fractal dimension converges to 2.0

radius of the unit disk around the half of the wavelength of the signal. For a single sine wave of 440hz, the half of its wave length is $1000/440/2 = 1.14(ms)$. We can find that the EMFD histogram of 440hz sine wave converges 2.0 at around 1.14 (ms) in Fig. 7. Fig. 8 explains this property of EMFD. When the radius of the unit disk is more than $500/frequency$, even if the radius increases, the area of Minkowski Sausage becomes nearly constant. Therefore the fractal dimension converges 2.0 by equation (2).

4.2 Robustness of EMFD against Volume Level and Phase Shifting

To analyze various types of environmental sounds with EMFD and for more reliable evaluation of the descriptiveness of EMFD in chapter 5, we demonstrate the robustness of EMFD against changing volume levels and phase shifting of sound signals. To test sounds with different volume levels, we prepared 3 sine waves of 110hz, 440hz and 1760hz with maximum volume of -0.1db. We duplicated the sound files and damp the signal level to -12db ($\approx 1/4$) and -24db ($\approx 1/16$) for the test. In Fig. 9, the three of EMFD histograms in the upper row show the test results. The original signal (black line) and the signal damped to -12db (dark

gray line) show almost the same EMFD at any frequency. There seems to be difference between the original signal and the signal damped to -24db (light gray line) especially with a large radius of the unit disk. The difference of the fractal dimension is no more than 3.12% ($r = 132, 440hz$). If the sound amplitude is reduced to 1/16, the impression in hearing the sound should be totally different. Therefore we may conclude that EMFD has enough robustness against changing volume levels.

Next we applied EMFD to single sine waves of 60hz, 180hz and 540hz with their phase shifted by 0 (black line), $\pi/4$ (dark gray line) and $\pi/2$ (light gray line). In Fig. 9, the three of EMFD histograms in the lower row show the test results. The lower the frequency of signal is, the bigger its impact from the difference between the phase of signal and scanning window is. The difference of the fractal dimension is no more than 1.07% ($r = 132, 60hz$). And if the frequency is higher than 400hz, we can find vanishingly small difference only in the histograms. For practical purposes, EMFD has enough robustness against phase shifting to scanning window.

5. EVALUATION OF DESCRIPTIVENESS OF EMFD SIGNATURE

To evaluate the descriptiveness of EMFD signature, we have developed a similarity search system using the k-nearest neighbors method. As a sound dataset, sufficient numbers of environmental sounds with metadata have been imported to the search system via Freesound API [8]. We evaluated the descriptiveness of acoustic features based on the similarity index we defined between tag groups of search-key sound and that of the retrieved sounds.

5.1 Sound Dataset

To collect environmental sounds for the sound dataset, we chose the Freesound project [9]. The database of Freesound stores many types of sounds uploaded by users. Freesound allows users to share their recording sounds and to describe metadata about shared sounds on the web. Each sound in this database is labeled with a group of tags, and they are relatively well maintained as user generated contents [10]. By utilizing Freesound API, applications can access the database of Freesound easily.

Based on the rules we defined, the sounds and its metadata were imported to our search system. The rules are as follows. These imported sounds are tagged with field-recording. The length may be between 1 second and 600 seconds. We chose the top 3,000 sounds in descending order of downloaded number. After sounds were imported to the search system, each sound is converted to the uniformed format (1 channel, sampling rate at 44,100hz, bit depth is 16bits with volume adjustment) for normalization to extract acoustic features including EMFD. The average length of imported sounds is 70.4 seconds.

5.2 Acoustic Features

The most well known feature for speech recognition and music classification may be mel-frequency cepstral coeffi-

Figure 9. EMFD histograms to estimate the robustness. The upper row: Difference for changing volume levels. The lower row: Difference for phase shifting to scanning window.

icients (MFCC) [11]. We chose MFCC for the comparison of descriptiveness with our EMFD-LL. We computed the standard 13 MFCC coefficients with their first and second derivatives. It is called MFCC39. The EMFD-LL is a feature vector consisting of 512 elements as mentioned in the sub section 3.4. To achieve the best possible performance of searching tasks by k-NN method, we applied Principal Components Analysis (PCA) for feature vector of top 600 sounds (in descending order of downloaded number) in dataset to reduce their dimensionality. For the feature sets of EMFD-LL + MFCC39, PCA is applied for the concatenated original feature vectors. Table 1 shows the acoustic feature sets and the length of its feature vectors.

	Feature Sets	L1	L2
1	EMFD-LL	512	72
2	MFCC39 (13MFCC+13Δ+13ΔΔ)	39	12
3	EMFD-LL + MFCC39	551	74

Table 1. List of acoustic feature sets for the comparison of descriptiveness of them. L1 is the length of concatenated original feature sets. L2 is the length of the feature vector after applying PCA.

5.3 Evaluation Method

We have developed a similarity search system based on the k-NN method using respective features as mentioned above. When user chooses any sound in dataset and its feature set via web browser, the search result list based on the selected feature set is shown instantly.

To evaluate the descriptiveness of each feature set, we defined the similarity index between the tag group of the search-key sound and that of the retrieved sounds. To compute the similarity index between tag groups, we utilized

the Natural Language Tool Kit (NLTK) [12] with a lexical database WordNet [13].

The similarity between tag_1 and tag_2 is defined as equation (9). The function of *path_similarity* provided by NLTK returns a score denoting how similar two synonym groups are, based on the shortest path that connects the meanings in the is-a taxonomy. Two synonym groups c_1 and c_2 denote those with tag_1 and tag_2 respectively as their elements. Then similarity between tag groups is defined by equation (10) and the similarity index between the tag group of the search-key sound and that of each retrieved sound in its search result list is defined as equation (11). The symbol s denotes the search-key sound and rs denotes the retrieved sounds in the search result list. The closer the meaning similarity of tag groups between search-key sound and each retrieved sound is, the bigger the similarity index is.

$$sim_{tag}(tag_1, tag_2) = \max_{c_1, c_2} \{path_similarity(c_1, c_2)\} \tag{9}$$

$$sim_{taggroup}(tags_1, tags_2) = \frac{\sum_{t_1 \in tags_1} \max_{t_2 \in tags_2} \{sim_{tag}(t_1, t_2)\}}{card(tags_1)} \tag{10}$$

$$sim_{sound}(s, rs) = \frac{sim_{taggroup}(tags_s, tags_{res})}{card(rs)} \tag{11}$$

5.4 Evaluation Results

For each of 3,000 sounds in the dataset, we computed the similarity index between itself as a search-key and each

retrieved sound in search result list. Fig. 10 shows the average values of the similarity index for each feature set. The values in the column “top n” are the average values of the similarity indices that a search-key sound and retrieved sound(s) in the top n rank in search result list. For reference, the average value of the similarity indices between the two randomly chosen sounds is 0.230.

Figure 10. The evaluation results of the similarity index

Furthermore, to analyze for which kind of environmental sounds the EMFD-LL can have good descriptiveness, we picked up tag groups based on the following procedures. Let $simE$ be the similarity index between a search-key sound and its top 10 retrieved results using EMFD-LL and $simM$ be that of MFCC39. Next we created two groups of sounds in the dataset, EMFD-LL Group gE and MFCC39 Group gM defined by equation (12).

$$gE = \{gE \in dataset \mid simE > simM\} \quad (12)$$

$$gM = \{gM \in dataset \mid simE < simM\}$$

Then we calculated the occurrence ratio for each tag labeling sounds in each group gE and gM . The occurrence ratio of each tag is defined as (number of occurrences of the tag labels to sounds in the group) / (number of sounds in the group). Let $oct(g, tag)$ be the function returns the occurrence ratio of the tag in group g . We picked up tag groups based on the equation (13). The parameter a is an optional coefficient to narrow down the options to choose tags. It seems that EMFD-LL can describe well the features of sound labeled with some tags in $T(a)$.

$$T(a) = \{tag \mid oct(gE, tag) > oct(gM, tag) \times a\} \quad (13)$$

We made sound groups with tags picked up and compute the similarity index for each sound group. As a result, we found that sound groups that EMFD-LL is obviously effective include, for example, {frog, frogs}, {children, child} and {waves, beach, sea, ocean}. Fig. 11 shows the similarity index of each group.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed the acoustic feature signature EMFD based on the MFD and demonstrated the basic characteristics of EMFD. To evaluate the descriptiveness of

Figure 11. The evaluation results of the similarity index for sound groups for which EMFD-LL is obviously effective.

EMFD signature of the environmental sounds, we developed the similarity search system using k-NN method and the similarity index. From the evaluation results, we found that the descriptiveness of EMFD-LL+MFCC39 is higher than that of MFCC39. Furthermore, for the sounds tagged with, for example, flogs, children, waves, beach, sea and ocean, the descriptiveness of EMFD-LL is obviously higher than that of MFCC39. Our goal is to improve the method to utilize EMFD and to improve the descriptiveness of EMFD so that we achieve the similarity search system for the environmental sounds with better performance. For our future research, we intend to trace the unique properties of the descriptiveness of EMFD and develop the improved signature with lower dimensionality.

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